

Developing Principles for Responsible Investment in Coastal and Marine Natural Capital

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Executive Summary

Scotland's marine and coastal ecosystems underpin a healthy, productive and resilient economy and society. They provide essential services including climate regulation and carbon storage, fisheries and food production, coastal protection, biodiversity, renewable energy space, and opportunities for tourism and recreation. These systems are dynamic and interconnected, with benefits and pressures flowing across land, coast and sea. Scotland has committed to halting biodiversity loss by 2030 and restoring ecosystems by 2045, but achieving these ambitions will require sustained investment at a time of significant pressure on public finances.

In response, the Scottish Government's Natural Capital Market Framework (2024) signals a growing role for responsible, values-led private investment to complement public funding. The accompanying Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital set clear expectations around environmental integrity, community engagement, ethical practice and public benefit. However, these principles were developed primarily under terrestrial contexts. At the same time, interest in mobilising private investment for marine and coastal restoration is accelerating, reflected in the Draft Marine and Coastal Restoration Plan and emerging blue carbon initiatives.

This policy brief examines how Scotland's existing principles can be meaningfully adapted for coastal and marine environments. It adopts a Source-to-Sea perspective, recognising that environmental outcomes are shaped by interactions across land, coast and sea, and that governance and investment frameworks must reflect these connections. The brief focuses on a natural capital approach to nature finance: private investment for environmental outcomes guided by natural capital principles and designed to deliver multiple ecological and societal benefits, with transparency, integrity and long-term stewardship. The emphasis is on the conditions under which finance is mobilised and governed, rather than on any single financial mechanism. This policy brief is intended for policymakers, regulators and public agencies responsible for Scotland's coastal and marine environment, including the Scottish Government, NatureScot, Crown Estate Scotland, SEPA, local authorities and regional marine planning partnerships. It will also be of interest to practitioners, researchers, community organisations and responsible investors engaged in marine and coastal restoration and stewardship.

The outputs presented here draw on a cross-sector workshop convened in May 2025, involving academics, policymakers, regulators, practitioners and industry. Discussions highlighted a consistent set of challenges that distinguish coastal and marine contexts from land-based nature finance. These include the limited availability of marine-specific standards and verification frameworks; a tendency to prioritise active intervention and easily measured outcomes (particularly carbon), despite evidence that pressure reduction and passive recovery are often more effective; persistent gaps in ecological and social baseline data; and misalignment between short-term financial expectations and long-term, non-linear ecological recovery. Governance complexity, diffuse and non-geographically anchored communities, and unclear benefit-sharing arrangements further complicate delivery.

At the same time, these challenges point to clear opportunities. Scotland already has well-established marine governance frameworks, including marine planning, licensing and seabed leasing, that provide practical entry points for embedding shared expectations. There is strong support for developing coastal and marine-specific restoration and recovery standards,

alongside stewardship-based approaches that reward long-term ecosystem care, pressure reduction and preventative action. Participants emphasised the value of phased, place-based pilot programmes, co-designed with communities, regulators and investors, to support learning by doing while maintaining transparency and ecological credibility. Across discussions, it was clear that adapting principles from land to coast and sea is not only a technical exercise, but also an ecological and social one. Social effectiveness in marine contexts must encompass both place-based community benefits and wider societal benefits, recognising that marine ecosystems deliver public goods across scales and that affected communities may be dispersed or overlapping.

The revised principles presented in this brief respond directly to these insights. They do not prescribe specific financial instruments, codes or regulatory applications. Instead, they set out a shared framework to guide how private investment for environmental outcomes should be designed, governed and evaluated in coastal and marine settings, so that ecological integrity, social legitimacy and long-term stewardship are not compromised in pursuit of short-term or narrowly defined gains. On this basis, the brief proposes a revised set of Principles for Responsible Investment in Coastal and Marine Natural Capital:

Investment that delivers integrated use

- Natural capital investment and management decisions should be informed by an understanding of positive and negative impacts, and of trade-offs and synergies across and within the four capitals (natural, social, economic and human), and between different marine and coastal users
- Natural capital investment and management decisions should deliver a range of environmental, social and economic outcomes.
- Natural capital investment and management decisions should reflect local conditions, acknowledge the suitability of coastal and marine space for particular uses, and protect and enhance existing natural capital.

Investment that demonstrates meaningful engagement and collaboration

- When acquiring new leases or designing and implementing projects, investors and delivery partners should engage early, fairly and meaningfully with communities and wider stakeholders affected by changes to marine and coastal use, to identify opportunities for shared benefit.
- This includes allocating sufficient time and resources to support genuine participation and community inclusion in shaping projects, consistent with emerging good practice such as the Community Inclusion Standard. Engagement should be undertaken within, and aligned to, relevant marine planning, consenting, licensing and leasing processes.
- Investors should collaborate openly with other coastal and marine users, beneficiaries and public bodies, and within relevant statutory and non-statutory policy frameworks, including marine planning, licensing and leasing, to contribute to a coherent approach to delivering benefits.
- Engagement should be undertaken in a manner consistent with the principles of a Social Licence to Operate, recognising that legitimacy, trust and demonstrable local and

societal benefit are essential to fair decision-making and long-term project viability, even where full consensus is not achievable.

Investment that delivers public, private and societal benefit

- Investment in and use of Scotland's natural capital should deliver benefits that are shared across public, private and societal interests, contributing to a just transition through transparent decision-making that demonstrates how benefits, impacts and trade-offs are addressed.
- Current investment and future management should enhance the function and accessibility of ecosystem services, delivering benefits for both local communities and wider society.
- Investment and management decisions should support Community Wealth Building by enabling the creation and long-term reinvestment of value in local economies.

Investment that is ethical and values led

- Investors should meet the six UN principles for responsible investment.
- As before: Investment should comply with the values of Scottish Government as set out by our policies on just transition, fair work and land rights & responsibilities as translated to marine systems.
- Public sector-influenced funds dedicated to natural capital in Scotland should establish clear ethical contribution policies, as exemplified by the 'Scottish Marine Environment Enhancement Fund' (SMEEF). These policies must outline the criteria for accepting and rejecting contributions, ensuring that donations align with the fund's core objectives and maintain trust in the fund, its projects, and its participants.

Investment that is of high long-term environmental integrity

- Investment in marine and coastal natural capital must be of high environmental integrity, guided by the mitigation hierarchy, and demonstrably contribute to long-term environmental improvement.
- Investment should not be used as a substitute for avoiding and reducing environmental harm at source. It must be additional to demonstrable actions to prevent, minimise or manage pressures and emissions, in line with relevant regulatory and policy frameworks.
- Investments can support active restoration as well as pressure reduction that supports passive recovery, where these lead to sustained environmental gains.
- Success should be assessed relative to ecological and environmental trends, not static baselines, and must account for source-to-sea connectivity to reflect effects, dependencies, and benefit-flow between land and sea.
- Projects must follow government-backed codes (e.g. biodiversity, carbon, nutrient) where available, and investors should seek professional advice, use reputable brokers, and secure all appropriate rights and licences.
- Any transfer of rights or credits must be recorded and disclosed through an open transparent mechanism such as through the UK Carbon Registry.

Investment that supports diverse and beneficial ownership, access and use

- Natural capital investment and management decisions should consider whether ownership or exclusive control is necessary when seeking to secure improvements in natural capital value. Where possible, they should prioritise management agreements, leasing, stewardship or partnership models with existing owners, tenants, users, delivery organisations or public bodies that can deliver wider social, economic and environmental benefit.
- When acquiring and/or managing land above Mean High Water Springs investors should have full regard to the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement and the expectations for responsible practice set out in the Scottish Land Commission's Land Rights and Responsibilities Protocols.
- Where leases, licences or other forma tenure or use rights are in place, investors should identify and engage relevant rights-holders and users early in decision-making and consider opportunities for shared benefit.

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Introduction

Scotland’s marine and coastal ecosystems play a vital role in supporting a healthy, productive and resilient economy and society. These ecosystems provide a variety of essential services including carbon storage and climate regulation, fisheries and food production, storm protection and coastal defence, biodiversity, renewable energy space and opportunities for tourism and recreation. These ecosystems are dynamic and interconnected, with many of the benefits, as well as pressures, flowing between land, coast and sea. The Scottish Government has set ambitious ecological goals, aiming to halt biodiversity loss by 2030 and to restore and regenerate ecosystems by 2045¹. Delivering these ambitions will require sustained public and private investment over many years at a time when public finances are under significant pressure.

In 2024, the Scottish Government published its Natural Capital Market Framework², signalling the role of responsible, values-led private investment to complement public funding and accelerate nature recovery. Within this, the finalised Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital³ were published which articulate expectations that private investment should deliver high environmental integrity, engage and collaborate with communities, provide public, private and community benefit, be ethical and values-led, support integrated land use, and contribute to diverse and productive ownership (Box 1). These principles were developed primarily with terrestrial contexts in mind.

Box 1: Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (2024)

- Principle 1: Investment that delivers integrated land use.
- Principle 2: Investment that demonstrates engagement and collaboration.
- Principle 3: Investment that delivers public, private and community benefit.
- Principle 4: Investment that is ethical and “values-led”.
- Principle 5: Investment that is of high environmental integrity.
- Principle 6: Investment that supports diverse and productive land ownership.

Currently, there is growing interest among industry, finance, the third sector and public agencies in unlocking private investment to support marine and coastal restoration. This is reflected by the Scottish Government’s Draft Marine and Coastal Restoration Plan⁴, the development of a Scottish Blue Carbon Action Plan and emerging work on a UK Saltmarsh Code⁵ based on blue-carbon benefits. In England, The Crown Estate has set out a roadmap for high-integrity marine natural capital markets⁶, highlighting the potential for seascape-scale restoration, blended finance models and regulatory levers to build investor confidence and market demand. There is growing policy interest in how compliance-based approaches, for example Marine Net Gain in England and Nature Positive Development and Use in Scotland, could act as incentive-based mechanisms for industry to demonstrate measurable improvements in the state of the coastal and marine environment.

Against this backdrop, this policy brief examines how Scotland’s existing Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital, could inform a coastal and marine-specific approach, acknowledging both the complementary and distinct opportunities and challenges in these environments. The brief identifies where terrestrial guidance holds and where coastal and marine-specific refinement is required. It takes a Source-to-Sea perspective, recognising that

environmental pressures, benefits and responsibilities flow across land, coast and sea, and that governance must reflect these connections. It also highlights the enabling conditions that could support a natural capital approach to nature finance that delivers restoration and enhancement in ways that are transparent, ecologically credible, socially just and aligned with Scotland's national priorities.

A natural capital approach to nature finance

Private investment for environmental outcomes that is guided by natural capital principles -designed to deliver multiple ecological and societal benefits, with transparency, integrity and long-term stewardship. This approach is not defined by any single financial mechanism but by the conditions under which finance is mobilised, governed and evaluated.

Private investment refers broadly to corporate funding, philanthropic contributions, partnerships and blended finance approaches that support environmental outcomes.

Figure 1. Benefits from the Seas wheel showing key ecosystem services provided by the marine environment. Source: NatureScot (with permission).

Audience

This brief is intended for policymakers and public agencies responsible for Scotland's coastal and marine environment, including the Scottish Government, NatureScot, Crown Estate Scotland, SEPA, local authorities and regional marine planning partnerships. It will also be of interest to practitioners, community organisations, researchers and responsible investors seeking clarity on the conditions under which private-sector investment can support restoration and enhancement of the coastal and marine environment.

Why principles matter

Experience from the development of voluntary private finance on land shows that investment interest can grow more rapidly than policy safeguards. While many early concerns have eased as standards have matured, debates around integrity, verification, trade-offs (such as carbon gains at biodiversity cost) and community impacts highlight the importance of clear, government-backed expectations. The Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital respond to

the growing recognition that private finance for nature must do more than enable transactions or discrete interventions; it must be shaped by clear expectations around ecological integrity, social legitimacy and long-term stewardship. Investment principles are not equivalent to technical methodologies or crediting standards. Whereas codes such as the Peatland Code or Woodland Carbon Code set out how specific outcomes (e.g. carbon sequestration) should be quantified, principles define the broader conditions under which nature finance should be designed, governed and evaluated. Extending the current Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital to coastal and marine environments is a necessary step. Coastal and marine ecosystems differ from terrestrial systems in fundamental ways: passive recovery and pressure reduction may be as or more ecologically effective than active restoration; baseline data are limited; outcomes are dynamic and long-term; community benefit may be diffuse or non-geographically anchored; and governance is complex and multi-sectoral. Ensuring that nature finance in coastal and marine environments reflects these realities requires an update of the existing principles.

Evidence base

Insights presented here draw on a cross-sector workshop convened in May 2025, supported by the Marine Alliance for Science and Technology for Scotland (MASTS) and Scotland Beyond Net Zero. The workshop brought together 28 researchers, policymakers, regulators, industry and practitioners to explore how Scotland's Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital could be meaningfully adapted and applied to the coastal and marine context. Over two days, discussions examined opportunities, risks and enabling conditions, and informed the development of a refined set of coastal and marine principles with associated rationale and near-term recommendations. Key risks, barriers and enabling actions identified through these discussions are summarised in Table 1 below accompanied by a more detailed discussion in Annex 1.

Table 1: Key risks and enabling actions identified through workshop discussions

Risk / Barrier	Enabling Condition / Opportunity
Lack of marine-specific codes and verification standards	Co-develop dedicated coastal and marine restoration and recovery codes (e.g. seagrass, saltmarsh, biodiversity uplift, water quality), building on emerging UK and international experience.
Focus of metric development on active intervention risks overlooking the often-greater ecological benefits of pressure removal and passive recovery	Pilot metrics and methodologies that explicitly recognise pressure reduction, passive restoration and system-level recovery pathways, and that align with longer ecological timelines.
Ecological complexity and non-linear recovery make crediting difficult	Test and refine whole-systems approaches to assessment that reflect ecological uncertainty, non-linear recovery trajectories and cumulative effects, rather than relying on narrow or short-term performance indicators.
Over-reliance on carbon as a measurable unit may sideline other benefits	Explore stewardship-based models that capture biodiversity, resilience, water quality and social co-benefits alongside carbon where appropriate.
Absence of baseline data limits ability to assess impact or additionality	Invest in long-term ecological and social monitoring and baseline studies, recognising that baselines must be adaptive and forward-looking to remain relevant under climate change and shifting ecosystem conditions. Funding could be supported through public investment or research-linked finance mechanisms.
Short-term investor expectations misaligned with long-term ecosystem recovery	Develop finance models with longer time horizons and adaptive management provisions that better reflect ecological recovery processes and uncertainty.
Lack of inclusive engagement with coastal communities and small-scale users	Ensure structured, early and sustained stakeholder participation in project design, delivery and benefit-sharing, with particular attention to under-represented and less-resourced users.

Unclear benefit-sharing in marine or non-residential settings	Redefine benefit-sharing to include non-geographic outcomes (e.g. general uplift in ecosystem services education, employment, stewardship roles) alongside place-based benefits where relevant.
No independent oversight of emerging marine investments	Clarify and coordinate the roles of existing public bodies (e.g. Marine Directorate, Crown Estate Scotland, NatureScot, JNCC, SEPA) to support oversight, mapping and transparent reporting of activity and outcomes, noting that any additional responsibilities must be adequately resourced and, where appropriate, funded through the investment process to avoid capacity constraints.
Weak or uncertain demand signals for marine nature finance	Explore the role of compliance-based mechanisms (e.g. through NPF4 for coastal development and National Marine Plan 2 for marine activity) and align incentives through policy and regulation to provide clearer signals and reduce reliance on voluntary uptake alone.
Fragmented governance and institutional uncertainty	Embed principles within existing frameworks (MSP, leasing, licensing) to mainstream accountability and integration
Siloed terrestrial and marine finance systems and dialogue.	Build source-to-sea principles into both terrestrial and marine frameworks, and associated codes and metrics work, for efficiencies and synergies that reflect the inherent connectivity, effects and dependencies that flow between land and sea.

Framing the principles for coastal and marine contexts

The principles that follow should be read in light of the challenges and opportunities outlined above. Translating principles for responsible investment from land to coast and sea is not simply a technical exercise: it requires attention to interconnected ecosystems, diffuse benefits, complex governance arrangements and long ecological timescales. Coastal and marine environments are characterised by shared space, overlapping uses and rights, and pressures that are often mobile, cumulative and difficult to isolate or exclude. As a result, investment decisions in these environments must account for spatial, temporal and cross-sectoral interactions in ways that differ fundamentally from many terrestrial contexts.

Workshop participants consistently emphasised that the principles should be interpreted and applied through a nature-led lens, meaning that ecological condition, system functioning and long-term resilience must be central to decision-making. While the principles do not explicitly prioritise nature above all other objectives, they are intended to be applied in ways that avoid compromising ecological integrity in pursuit of short-term or narrowly defined outcomes.

Consistent with the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy, and reflecting the particular characteristics of coastal and marine systems, the principles are grounded in an ecosystem approach. This approach recognises that marine and coastal environments function as interconnected systems, where pressures, recovery processes and benefits are often diffuse, non-linear. In these contexts, focusing narrowly on individual habitats, species or metrics risks overlooking system-level dynamics that are critical to long-term recovery and resilience. Explicitly adopting an ecosystem approach therefore represents a necessary refinement of existing terrestrial-focused guidance, rather than a departure from it.

For consistency, the principles are presented in the same sequence as the existing Scottish Government Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital. This ordering should not be read as implying a hierarchy of importance.

Investment that delivers integrated use

Current Principle: Investment that delivers integrated land use	Proposed Principle: Investment that delivers integrated use
Investment and management decisions should demonstrate consideration of positive and negative impacts across all four capitals (natural, social, economic, human).	Natural capital investment and management decisions should be informed by an understanding of positive and negative impacts, and of trade-offs and synergies across and within the four capitals (natural, social, economic and human), and between different marine and coastal users
Carbon management should be integrated with delivery of wider environmental, social and economic outcomes, such as biodiversity improvements, resilience to food supply and natural flood management.	Natural capital investment and management decisions should deliver a range of environmental, social and economic outcomes.
Investment and management decisions should recognise and respond to local circumstances, acknowledge the suitability of land for particular uses and seek to	Natural capital investment and management decisions should reflect local conditions, acknowledge the suitability of coastal and marine space for particular

protect and enhance existing natural capital.	uses, and protect and enhance existing natural capital.
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This principle updates the original focus on integrated land use to reflect the dynamic, shared and multi-use nature of coastal and marine environments. These systems are shaped by overlapping rights, seasonal variability and diverse sectoral demands, including fishing, tourism, offshore energy and conservation. An integrated use approach in the marine context therefore needs to account for spatial, temporal and cross-sectoral interactions.

The revised principle places greater emphasis on recognising trade-offs and synergies across and within the four capitals, acknowledging that investment decisions in coastal and marine settings often involve balancing multiple objectives and stakeholders within a shared space. It also broadens the outcome focus beyond carbon to encompass a wider range of environmental, social and economic benefits.

Importantly, the revision shifts from a passive emphasis on “seeking to protect” natural capital towards an active commitment to protecting and enhancing it through long-term stewardship. It reinforces the need for investment decisions to be appropriate to context, recognising the distinct ecological conditions, patterns of use and community priorities that characterise nearshore environments, while ensuring that offshore decisions are responsive to wider-scale ecological processes, sectoral interactions and strategic marine planning.

Investment that demonstrates meaningful engagement and collaboration

Current Principle: Investment that demonstrates engagement and collaboration	Proposed Principle: Investment that demonstrates meaningful engagement and collaboration
Investors and land managers should engage with local communities in decisions about land and land use change, in line with the Scottish Government’s Guidance on Engaging Communities in Decisions Relating to Land.	When acquiring new leases or designing and implementing projects, investors and delivery partners should engage early, fairly and meaningfully with communities and wider stakeholders affected by changes to

<p>When acquiring new land, investors should seek early engagement with relevant local communities to inform future plans and identify opportunities to collaborate in delivering community benefit.</p>	<p>marine and coastal use, to identify opportunities for shared benefit.</p> <p>This includes allocating sufficient time and resources to support genuine participation and community inclusion in shaping projects, consistent with emerging good practice such as the Community Inclusion Standard. Engagement should be undertaken within, and aligned to, relevant marine planning, consenting, licensing and leasing processes.</p>
<p>Investors and land managers should collaborate openly with other landowners and public bodies to contribute to a coherent approach to delivering benefits.</p>	<p>Investors and delivery partners should collaborate openly with other coastal and marine users, beneficiaries and public bodies, and within relevant statutory and non-statutory policy frameworks, including marine planning, licensing and leasing, to contribute to a coherent approach to delivering benefits.</p>
	<p>Engagement should be undertaken in a manner consistent with the principles of a Social Licence to Operate, recognising that legitimacy, trust and demonstrable local and societal benefit are essential to fair decision-making and long-term project viability, even where full consensus is not achievable.</p>

This principle revises the original land-focused guidance on engagement and collaboration to reflect the governance complexity of coastal and marine environments, where ownership, rights and decision-making frameworks differ markedly from terrestrial contexts. While it builds on the original emphasis on community and stakeholder engagement and inclusion, it adapts this guidance to the distinct institutional, spatial and social realities of marine and coastal settings.

Unlike land-based projects, where engagement often centres on neighbouring, place-based communities, coastal and marine projects must account for a broader, more diverse and often more dispersed range of stakeholders, particularly offshore. In addition to local coastal communities, these may include fishers, aquaculture operators, recreational users, environmental NGOs, and small-scale or informal users whose rights may not be formally recognised, but whose livelihoods and cultural connections to the sea are significant.

This principle recognises that effective engagement is not just procedural but relational. Securing legitimacy, trust and shared value depends on sustained dialogue, transparency, and fair

processes, not just one-off consultations. The concept of a Social Licence to Operate offers a useful lens here: it highlights the importance of going beyond legal compliance to earn public trust and social acceptance, particularly in sectors with visible environmental or social impacts⁷.

Workshop participants also underscored the importance of addressing power asymmetries, which shape investment decisions across both land and sea. There is a risk that dominant actors may crowd out or marginalise underrepresented groups. To mitigate this, engagement must be early, inclusive and adequately resourced, with careful attention to how short-term economic gains and longer-term economic stability and sustainability are distributed, and who stands to gain or lose from investment activity. Where existing users may be impacted, engagement and inclusion strategies should include transparent processes that address both opportunities for benefit-sharing and clear plans to identify, mitigate and manage adverse impacts, consistent with principles of fairness and just transition (see Principles 3 and 4).

In terrestrial and nearshore coastal areas, existing Scottish Government guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land use change remains appropriate and relevant. In these contexts, expectations around early and meaningful community engagement broadly mirror those set out in the original Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital. *“Investors and land managers should engage with local communities in decisions about land and land use change, in line with the Scottish Government’s Guidance on Engaging Communities in Decisions Relating to Land.”*

However, marine environments, including the foreshore, seabed and water column, are governed through distinct statutory frameworks, notably marine planning, licensing and leasing. Approximately half of Scotland’s foreshore is privately owned, while the remainder forms part of the Scottish Crown Estate and is managed by Crown Estate Scotland on behalf of Scottish Ministers. Beyond the foreshore, the seabed is managed by Crown Estate Scotland. These arrangements mean that “private land” concepts do not transfer neatly to marine settings, and engagement expectations must reflect the specific governance pathways through which decisions are made including marine planning, licensing and leasing.

While assets managed by Crown Estate Scotland are held in trust for the nation and intended to deliver public benefit, workshop discussions highlighted the importance of clearly articulating expectations around meaningful engagement, inclusion and benefit-sharing for activities occurring on or affecting the seabed and marine space. The revised principle is not intended to redefine statutory roles or ownership arrangements, but to ensure that investment and delivery decisions, regardless of ownership, are underpinned by inclusive, context-appropriate engagement that supports legitimacy, trust and long-term stewardship.

While engagement approaches may differ between offshore and nearshore projects, the principle reinforces that procedural fairness and collaborative governance are essential across land, coast, and sea.

Investment that delivers public, private and societal benefit

Current Principle: Investment that delivers public, private and community benefit	Proposed Principle: Investment that delivers public, private and societal benefit
Investment in and use of Scotland’s natural capital should create benefits that are shared between public, private and community interests, contributing to a just transition.	Investment in and use of Scotland’s natural capital should deliver benefits that are shared across public, private and societal interests, contributing to a just transition through transparent decision-making that demonstrates how benefits, impacts and trade-offs are addressed.
Current investment and future increases in land and ecosystem services value should benefit local communities.	Current investment and future management should enhance the function and accessibility of marine and coastal ecosystem services, delivering benefits for both local communities and wider society.
Investment and management decisions should support Community Wealth Building by reinvesting value in local economies to their long-term benefit.	Investment and management decisions should support Community Wealth Building by enabling the creation and long-term reinvestment of value in local economies.

This principle builds on the original focus on delivering community, public and private benefit, but adapts it to the spatial and governance complexity of Scotland’s marine and coastal environments. In these settings, investment often creates new value streams rather than interacting with established land-based economies, making it essential to be explicit about how value is generated, distributed and retained over the long term.

In coastal areas, there is likely to be greater overlap between investment activities and identifiable local communities, particularly where projects occur on or adjacent to privately owned land (above high water). In these settings, it may still be appropriate to apply land-based definitions of community benefit (e.g. via the Scottish Land Commission⁸).

In contrast, in marine environment, there is no ownership, instead statutory licensing and leasing frameworks shape access to and use of marine space. In these contexts, benefit-sharing is less about land ownership and more about how value derived from shared marine resources is distributed. In this context, the notion of “community” requires careful reinterpretation. While place-based community benefits remain important in many coastal settings, particularly where private ownership exists, many investments in marine natural capital (for example offshore restoration, fisheries enhancement, water quality improvement or seabed recovery) are less likely to connect to a single geographic community. Instead, benefits and impacts are often diffuse and shared across public, private and societal interests.

Public benefit refers to outcomes that deliver collective value, including the full suite of ecosystem services such as environmental integrity, ecosystem resilience, climate regulation and other public goods. Societal benefit captures wider social outcomes beyond formal public goods, including distributional effects, cultural values, wellbeing, livelihoods and fairness across different groups and scales. This framing recognises that marine and coastal benefits and impacts are frequently experienced across society rather than by geographically fixed populations alone.

As a result, this revised principle encourages a more flexible and layered understanding of who benefits. It expands the framing from “community” to “public, private, and societal” benefit, recognising that investments in natural capital can and should contribute to wider public and societal goods, including ecological resilience, national wellbeing, and economic diversification. Where direct, place-based community benefits are not feasible, delivering demonstrable long-term environmental and public value should be recognised as a legitimate form of social return. Importantly, benefit should not be understood narrowly as financial. Investment should also support communities and sectors experiencing marine change through skills development, local employment, infrastructure and nature-based enterprise opportunities, aligning with the aims of Community Wealth Building (Scotland) Bill⁹, to retain and reinvest value over the long term.

Investment that is ethical and values led

Current Principle: Investment that is ethical and values led	Proposed Principle: Investment that is ethical and values led
Investors should meet the six UN principles for responsible investment	<i>As before:</i> Investors should meet the six UN principles for responsible investment ¹⁰
Investment should comply with the values of Scottish Government as set out by our policies on just transition ¹ , fair work and land rights & responsibilities.	<i>As before:</i> Investment should comply with the values of Scottish Government as set out by our policies on just transition ¹¹ , fair work ¹² and land rights & responsibilities ¹³ as translated to marine systems.
Public sector-influenced funds dedicated to natural capital in Scotland should establish clear ethical contribution policies, as exemplified by the ‘Scottish Marine Environment Enhancement Fund’ (SMEEF). These policies must outline the criteria for accepting and rejecting contributions, ensuring that donations align with the fund’s core objectives and maintain trust in the fund, its projects, and its participants.	<i>As before:</i> Public sector-influenced funds dedicated to natural capital in Scotland should establish clear ethical contribution policies, as exemplified by the ‘Scottish Marine Environment Enhancement Fund’ (SMEEF). These policies must outline the criteria for accepting and rejecting contributions, ensuring that donations align with the fund’s core objectives and maintain

	trust in the fund, its projects, and its participants.
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While the ethical foundations of responsible investment apply equally across land and sea, poor practice in marine and coastal environments can have amplified consequences due to public ownership, limited visibility, complex governance arrangements and long ecological timescales. This principle therefore remains unchanged in wording but requires contextual clarification to support its meaningful application in coastal and marine settings. The original intent—that investment should align with the values set out in Scottish Government policy—is equally relevant. However, workshop discussions highlighted important questions about how such values are defined, interpreted and applied in practice, particularly across diverse coastal and marine contexts. Participants emphasised the need to consider whose values and knowledge systems inform judgements about what constitutes “ethical” investment.

The existing principles refer to Scotland’s Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement, which promotes a values-led approach to land ownership, access and use. While there is no direct marine equivalent, many of the underlying principles, stewardship, public benefit, transparency and engagement, are equally relevant in coastal and marine contexts. In marine settings, where there is no private ownership in the terrestrial sense, governance places greater emphasis on access, use and shared responsibility, as reflected in frameworks such as the Marine (Scotland) Act, marine planning and international obligations under UNCLOS (United Nations Convention on Law of the Sea_.

This principle therefore adapts the ethical and values-led intent of the terrestrial guidance to reflect the realities of marine governance, where activities often affect shared resources, multiple users and culturally significant spaces. In these contexts, ethical investment requires particular attention to transparency, accountability and the fair distribution of benefits and burdens arising from investment activity.

As previously discussed, the concept of Social Licence to Operate is especially relevant in the coastal and marine context, where investment activities may affect shared resources or displace existing uses. Social licence extends the idea of legal compliance into the realm of public trust, legitimacy, and ongoing consent, recognising that acceptance may evolve as projects and management arrangements develop. Embedding ethical approaches that support social licence, such as inclusive engagement, transparency and mechanisms for sustained dialogue, can reduce conflict, support just outcomes and improve project outcomes

Workshop participants also raised concerns around equity between marine sectors. Ethical investment must consider not only environmental impacts, but who is affected by decisions about marine space and resources. In marine contexts, no sector holds outright ownership; instead, access and use are mediated through different forms of permission, licensing or leasing, often with varying degrees of security, duration and influence. Ethical governance

should therefore avoid privileging actors with more visible or capital-intensive uses, or greater regulatory leverage, over sectors and communities with longstanding but less formally recognised relationships to the marine environment, such as inshore fisheries, recreational users, and cultural or heritage interests.

Finally, investment mechanisms supporting coastal and marine natural capital should maintain clear ethical contribution policies, setting out the types of donors and funding sources that align with the values and objectives of the Natural Capital Market Framework. Where mechanisms are public sector-influenced or publicly administered, such as SMEEF, there is a particular responsibility to lead by example, ensuring transparency, consistency and public trust in how finance is sourced and applied.

Investment that is of high long-term environmental integrity

Original Principle: Investment that is of high environmental integrity	Proposed Principle: Investment that is of high long-term environmental integrity
<p>Investment in offsetting should not be a replacement for emissions reductions, and should always be made in addition to having plans and demonstrable actions in place to <i>reduce</i> emissions as close to zero as possible, and as part of targets and transition plans aligned with the Paris Agreement and verifiable, such as through the government-backed Woodland Carbon Code and the Peatland Code.</p>	<p>Investment in marine and coastal natural capital must be of high environmental integrity, guided by the mitigation hierarchy, and demonstrably contribute to long-term environmental improvement.</p>
	<p>Investment should not be used as a substitute for avoiding and reducing environmental harm at source. It must be additional to demonstrable actions to prevent, minimise or manage pressures and emissions, in line with relevant regulatory and policy frameworks.</p>
	<p>Investments can support active restoration as well as pressure reduction that supports passive recovery, where these lead to sustained environmental gains.</p>
	<p>Success should be assessed relative to ecological and environmental trends, not static baselines, and must account for source-to-sea connectivity to reflect effects, dependencies, and benefit-flow between land and sea.</p>

<p>When considering investment or trades, stakeholders should seek professional advice and use established Codes and reputable brokers.</p>	<p>Projects must follow government-backed codes (e.g. biodiversity, carbon, nutrient) where available, and investors should seek professional advice, use reputable brokers, and secure all appropriate rights and licences.</p>
<p>Land owners considering the sale of carbon credits should consider their own current and future carbon management needs before doing so.</p>	<p><i>Principle not relevant to this context</i></p> <p>The statement was removed because mitigation hierarchy and integrity standards already address the underlying risk. Requiring sellers to assess their own future carbon needs is not standard practice in existing codes and is poorly suited to marine contexts, where benefits are often system-wide and not tied to individual emitters.</p>
<p>Where rights to or control over carbon or other natural capital are transferred to a third party, this information should be made available in an open and transparent way such as through the UK Carbon Registry.</p>	<p>Any transfer of rights or credits must be recorded and disclosed through an open transparent mechanism such as through the UK Carbon Registry</p>

This principle retains a focus on verified, lasting environmental outcomes but broadens the framing beyond carbon to reflect whole-system integrity. Across land, coast and sea, environmental integrity must encompass biodiversity, ecosystem functioning and long-term resilience. In coastal and marine contexts, this requires explicit recognition of cumulative pressures, source-to-sea dynamics and climate-related risks that shape ecological condition and recovery over time.

The revised wording reinforces the primacy of the mitigation hierarchy, making clear that natural capital investment must not substitute for avoiding and reducing harm at source where impacts occur. Workshop discussions acknowledged that some investment may be motivated by voluntary contributions to nature recovery or “nature-positive” goals that are not linked to offsetting specific impacts. While such contributions can play a constructive role, they do not displace the obligation to follow the mitigation hierarchy where environmental harm arises.

Alignment with trusted codes, standards and verification processes is essential to maintaining environmental integrity. However, participants noted that fit-for-purpose marine and coastal frameworks, registries and governance infrastructure remain underdeveloped, creating a practical barrier to full implementation in the near term. At present, robust public registries exist primarily for carbon (e.g. the UK Carbon Registry), while equivalent mechanisms for biodiversity and wider natural capital outcomes are still emerging. Ongoing work under the Woodland Carbon Code and Peatland Code to develop biodiversity quantification and dual-outcome approaches

illustrates how registries may evolve, with potential relevance for future coastal and marine codes. Until such mechanisms are established, this principle sets a clear expectation that any transfer of rights or credits should be recorded and disclosed through the most appropriate open and transparent system available.

The original statement advising landowners to consider their own current and future carbon management needs before selling credits has been removed. In coastal and marine contexts, this concept is often unclear or inapplicable, as project developers are frequently not primary emitters and benefits are delivered at ecosystem or system scale. Retaining this wording risked ambiguity without strengthening safeguards. The revised principle therefore focuses on the appropriate locus of integrity: ensuring that investment does not replace avoidance and reduction of impacts at source.

Finally, the principle responds to a broader tension identified in the workshop between market requirements and ecological reality. While markets depend on clarity around metrics, additionality and permanence, marine and coastal ecosystems are dynamic and context-dependent. Environmental success must therefore be assessed over time and at system scale, using flexible and proportionate approaches to measurement where necessary, rather than relying solely on static baselines or narrow project-level accounting.

Investment that supports diverse and beneficial ownership, access and use

Original Principle: Investment that supports diverse and productive land ownership	Investment that supports diverse and beneficial ownership, access and use
<p>If seeking to secure carbon units or natural capital value, investors should consider whether ownership of land is necessary. Where possible they should consider opportunities for management agreements and collaboration/partnerships with communities that can deliver wider social and economic benefit.</p>	<p>Natural capital investment and management decisions should consider whether ownership or exclusive control is necessary when seeking to secure improvements in natural capital value. Where possible, they should prioritise management agreements, leasing, stewardship or partnership models with existing owners, tenants, users, delivery organisations or public bodies that can deliver wider social, economic and environmental benefit.</p>
<p>When acquiring and/or managing land, investors should have full regard to the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement and the expectations for responsible practice set out in the Scottish Land Commission's Land Rights and Responsibilities Protocols.</p>	<p>When acquiring and/or managing land above Mean High Water Springs investors should have full regard to the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement and the expectations for responsible practice set out in the Scottish Land Commission's Land Rights and Responsibilities Protocols.</p> <p><i>(Not applicable below mean high water springs)</i></p>
<p>Where there are leases or other forms of tenure in place, for example in agricultural tenancies or crofting tenure, investors should identify and engage relevant parties early in decision making and consider opportunities for shared benefit.</p>	<p>Where leases, licences or other forms of tenure or use rights are in place, investors should identify and engage relevant rights-holders and users early in decision-making and consider opportunities for shared benefit.</p>

For land above Mean High Water Springs, this principle is retained in substance from the original Scottish Government principle: Investment that supports diverse and productive land ownership. The revision clarifies its continued relevance in terrestrial and coastal settings where land ownership applies, while updating the language to reflect a broader focus on natural capital value rather than carbon units alone.

This principle remains highly relevant where nature finance and restoration investment interact with historically concentrated patterns of land ownership in rural and coastal Scotland. As highlighted by the Scottish Land Commission, such concentration can constrain sustainable development, limit community-led opportunity, and reduce the social legitimacy of investment. Retaining this principle helps ensure that natural capital investment on land supports diverse ownership and management models, encourages collaboration with existing owners, tenants and other rights-holders (including agricultural tenants and crofters), and aligns with Scotland's wider objectives for responsible land use and long-term stewardship.

Below Mean High Water Springs, the principle is necessarily reframed rather than directly translated, reflecting the fundamentally different legal and governance context of the marine environment. In contrast to terrestrial contexts, marine natural capital investment does not operate through land tenure or ownership. Instead, access and use are governed through marine planning, licensing and leasing systems, with the seabed owned by the Crown and managed on behalf of the public. As a result, the focus shifts from ownership to questions of access, use, representation and governance.

In this context, ensuring that investment supports a diverse, inclusive and beneficial mix of marine uses is essential for long-term legitimacy, ecological integrity and social acceptance. This includes recognising and accommodating a wide range of activities, such as fisheries, aquaculture, offshore energy, recreation and conservation, and ensuring that new investment models do not disproportionately benefit well-capitalised or dominant sectors at the expense of small-scale, mobile or less formally represented users.

Participants emphasised the need for early and meaningful engagement with existing marine users, particularly where seabed leases, marine licences or other spatial permissions are already in place, such as for offshore renewables, aquaculture, fisheries activity or marine infrastructure. They also highlighted opportunities to develop new models of coastal and marine stewardship, including shared management agreements and community co-benefit models, with existing livelihoods and uses.

Consistent with the principles of set out elsewhere in this brief, marine natural capital investment should deliver outcomes that contribute to public value, societal wellbeing and long-term stewardship of shared resources, not simply private returns. This reinforces the importance of inclusive governance, early engagement and transparent decision-making to ensure that benefits and impacts are fairly distributed across communities, sectors and society as a whole.

Ultimately, this principle affirms that equity of access, procedural fairness, and the recognition of diverse marine knowledge systems must be central to natural capital investment. By supporting a pluralistic and inclusive vision of marine space, it encourages markets that are not only economically viable, but socially legitimate and ecologically adaptive. It also positions

diverse marine use as a strength, helping to maintain cultural identity and ecosystem stewardship over the long term.

Pathway to impact: how these principles support change

The revised principles set out in this brief represent a practical step forward in applying a natural capital approach to nature finance in Scotland's coastal and marine environments. They clarify that responsible private investment for environmental outcomes must be ecologically credible, socially legitimate and oriented towards long-term stewardship, rather than short-term or narrowly defined gains.

The accompanying Theory of Change (Figure 2) illustrates how embedding these principles within policy, planning and investment decision-making can translate values-led intent into lasting ecological, social and economic benefits. Central to this pathway is a Source-to-Sea perspective, recognising that coastal and marine outcomes are shaped by land-based pressures, governance decisions and investment choices. Aligning these revised principles with Scotland's existing terrestrial frameworks provides an opportunity to move beyond carbon- or land-centric models and toward a more integrated approach to natural capital across land, coast and sea. Embedding the principles across marine planning, licensing, leasing, regulatory and funding frameworks offers a clear route to impact. Doing so can help ensure that emerging codes, standards and financing mechanisms support restoration and recovery in ways that are transparent, inclusive and aligned with public value, while providing confidence to investors, regulators and communities. Underpinning this pathway is a commitment to pragmatism and adaptive learning. Given ecological uncertainty, data limitations and evolving governance arrangements, no single framework will be perfect from the outset. The principles are therefore not an end point, but a shared starting point: a framework to guide responsible decision-making, enable learning by doing, and align investment with ecological integrity and community wellbeing. As Scotland continues to explore the role of nature finance in supporting healthy, resilient and productive coasts and seas, these principles provide a foundation from which inclusive, high-integrity and ecologically credible practice can grow. The Theory of Change is intended to illustrate a logical pathway for learning, alignment and capacity-building over time, rather than to imply fixed timelines or policy commitments.

Figure 1: Theory of Change for Principles for Responsible Investment in Coastal and Marine Natural Capital Markets

Annex 1: Navigating risks and unlocking opportunities: foundations for high-integrity marine natural capital investment

This annex provides a detailed synthesis of workshop discussions and literature, on the risks and enabling conditions associated with developing coastal and marine natural capital markets in Scotland.

Coastal and marine specific metrics, standards and verification

A consistent theme across workshop discussions was the limited availability of coastal- and marine-specific metrics, standards and verification frameworks to underpin high-integrity private investment in coastal and marine environments. Private investment on land has benefited from more mature frameworks, such as the Woodland Carbon Code and Peatland Code, whilst the coastal and marine investment in Scotland remains at an early stage in terms of codified approaches, baseline data and monitoring systems. This gap underscores the need for targeted research, co-development and piloting of standards and metrics tailored to coastal and marine ecosystems.

Recent UK work illustrates both the potential and current limitations. The emerging Saltmarsh Code¹⁴ led by the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, is currently structured around carbon benefits from managed realignment, with biodiversity, nutrient reduction and flood defence outcomes under consideration as part of a series of additional metrics alongside carbon. Likewise, the Seagrass Code^{15,16}, currently in development, has focused on carbon sequestration potential, reflecting the wider pattern in early land-based frameworks of using carbon as the most straightforward quantifiable metric, though it may not capture the full ecological value or local context of habitats. Examples of restoration efforts in Scotland, including the community-led Seawilding¹⁷ (Loch Craignish, Argyll and Loch Broom, Wester Ross), and community engaged initiatives such as Restoration Forth¹⁸ (Firth of Forth), demonstrate momentum in seagrass and oyster bed restoration and the development of practical restoration toolkits. These represent just some of a growing number of place-based initiatives across Scotland's coasts. While highly valuable, these projects are not yet embedded within formal investment frameworks, reflecting the formative stage of nature finance in marine environments.

Further lessons can be drawn from international experience. In Europe, there is a notable example of 'Label Bas-Carbone', a French voluntary carbon standard to recover seagrasses by removing and reducing the physical impacts from boating and anchoring, funded by carbon finance¹⁹. Yet, global reviews (e.g. Shilland et al., 2021²⁰), highlight that marine restoration projects often struggle to meet the stringent criteria required for outcome verification, such as additionality and permanence often due to insufficient ecological baselines and the early-stage nature of marine restoration science, as well as a lack of any mechanisms by which the site can be managed with a long-term protection guarantee.

Workshop participants also emphasised the risk that metric development is often focussed on active intervention and risks overlooking the often-greater ecological benefits of pressure removal and passive recovery. Participants emphasised that, unlike many terrestrial contexts where active restoration is a central pathway, the primary route to ecological recovery in marine systems is often the management or removal of pressures. For many habitats and species, it is

both ecologically and financially more effective to address the source of degradation than to undertake active restoration or enhancement. Recognising this distinction is critical for shaping nature finance in the coastal and marine environments.

A related and significant risk identified during the workshop is the persistent lack of baseline ecological, social, and economic data for many coastal and marine environments. This data gap makes it difficult to assess additionality, predict restoration outcomes, or develop credible metrics for monitoring change. Without robust, long-term datasets, there is a danger that investment decisions will be based on assumptions rather than evidence, increasing the risk of misjudged trade-offs, project failure, or ecological harm. Furthermore, marine ecosystems are naturally dynamic, with conditions varying across space and time, and climate change is accelerating shifts in species distributions, habitat structure and ecological functioning. Even where baselines exist, they may not remain stable or relevant under future climate scenarios. Furthermore, recovery in coastal and marine ecosystems is difficult to predict, and recovery trajectories are often non-linear. Yet financial instruments for supporting recovery are structured around short-term payback cycles and investor returns leading to a misalignment between ecological timelines and financial expectations. This highlights the need for investment frameworks that can accommodate variability, uncertainty and long-term ecological change.

An additional concern lies in the tendency on finance mechanisms to focus on what can be easily measured. While carbon offers a clear, commodifiable metric, many outcomes of coastal and marine restoration, such as ecological connectivity, biodiversity and increased resilience are far harder to quantify. Although biodiversity metrics exist and can be deployed in some contexts, their interpretation can be challenging in dynamic marine environments. At the workshop there was concern that an overemphasis on measurable metrics could inadvertently risk de-prioritising essential ecosystem functions, leading to investment models that neglect non-market benefits or overlook the complex interdependencies of marine systems. That said, if responsible nature finance is to attract investment at scale, there remains a need for standardised, verifiable metrics that give confidence and comparability to investors. As seen in the development of Woodland and Peatland Codes, the existence of a credible, verifiable credit has been key to enabling transactions and building trust. This tension between ecological complexity and financial standardisation raises important design questions: how can investment frameworks for coastal and marine ecosystems incorporate plural, holistic valuation systems, and avoid being limited by what is easily quantified or will they be constrained by the limits of what can be commodified?

Governance complexity, accountability and participation in marine decision-making

Compounding these uncertainties are the social and governance risks associated with stakeholder representation. Coastal and marine environments are inherently multi-use and politically complex. Without careful design, interventions may reinforce existing power asymmetries by failing to capture the inputs of small-scale fishers, coastal community initiatives and recreational or cultural users, many of whom lack the institutional voice needed to engage on equal footing. Participants also noted that many people who depend on, benefit from or value marine ecosystems do not necessarily identify themselves as “marine stakeholders,” yet their interests may be affected by changes in how marine space is used or financed. These challenges are sharpened by the difficulty of defining “community” in the marine environment. Unlike many

terrestrial contexts, where benefit-sharing is often geographically anchored, marine interventions may affect dispersed or overlapping communities of interest. Moreover, if adopting a Source-to-Sea perspective, land-based interventions could generate benefits (or even disbenefits downstream), meaning that geographically anchored models of community benefit are often insufficient when taking a Source-to-Sea lens. In Scotland, seabed development is governed through licensing for activities in the water by the Marine Directorate and NatureScot with leases offered by Crown Estate Scotland once licensing conditions are met. The management of non-development related activities are governed by a complex variety of regulatory and non-regulatory systems. This creates important questions about transparency, accountability and who is entitled to participate in, influence, or benefit from privately financed restoration and recovery activities. Without clear and inclusive governance frameworks, there is a risk that benefits accrue primarily to better-resourced or institutionally recognised actors, while those most directly affected, socially, culturally or economically, are excluded from decision-making or receive limited benefit.

Demand signals, voluntary action and policy timing

Finally, a structural risk underlies much of this discussion: are we developing Principles, Metrics and Investment Standards in a context where there is not yet a clear or consistent demand signal from investors? Current interest from investors remains exploratory and early-stage. While this may evolve over time, there is a danger of designing governance frameworks in a vacuum, prioritising theory over operational reality. This raises a critical policy dilemma: should government and partners focus first on developing standards, infrastructure and piloting activity to build confidence, or should stronger demand signals be established first, potentially through regulatory or compliance mechanisms, before investing heavily in codes, governance structures and oversight mechanisms.

Cross-Cutting risk and opportunity: scope and application of the principles

A key consideration emerging from the workshop discussions was the scope of application: who exactly should be expected to adopt and uphold the principles proposed in this policy brief? This question also applies to the existing terrestrial Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital.

Currently, the Scottish Government's Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital are primarily designed for private investors, particularly those engaged in carbon-focused restoration and enhancement actions. However, as highlighted at the workshop, applying to narrow a lens, focused only on voluntary private finance, risks overlooking other influential actors across land, coast, and sea and misses the opportunity to embed environmental accountability more widely.

This has the potential to create inconsistency: while voluntary nature finance actors are asked to meet high standards of transparency, measurement, verification, and social safeguards, other businesses operating in the same ecosystems (across land, sea and coast), are not always held to equivalent expectations, whether through regulation or other forms of governance. This asymmetry raises important questions about fairness, legitimacy and coherence across Scotland's environmental governance landscape.

Participants also highlighted the importance of clarity about the types of activities and interventions to which the principles are expected to apply. Discussion surfaced a distinction between actions focused on the seabed, such as habitat restoration, enhancement or pressure reduction and those primarily affecting the water column and mobile species, including fish. These domains involve different ecological dynamics, stakeholder groups and regulatory frameworks, and are often governed through distinct policy and management regimes. Greater clarity could support alignment with sectoral governance and help ensure that future metrics, monitoring approaches and benefit-sharing models are ecologically appropriate and socially legitimate for the type of intervention being undertaken.

This led to a broader, more forward-looking discussion: should the principles evolve into a shared framework of responsibility not only for investors, but also for public authorities, developers, sectoral users, community-led initiatives and other actors whose decisions affect natural capital? This broader application could support more consistent, transparent, and equitable decision-making across Scotland's land and sea and encourage a more integrated, systems-level approach to stewardship. Some participants noted that, over time, such principles could potentially be reinforced through compliance-based mechanisms. Compliance-based mechanisms for nature recovery have tended to be more successful than voluntary approaches alone because they create a clear regulatory obligation and enforceable standards. By introducing a legal or policy "stick," these have the potential to drive consistent action across sectors and reduce reliance on discretionary or reputational motivations alone. However, this would require further policy development and dialogue across sectors to align incentives, clarify roles, and ensure practicality.

A more immediate opportunity lies in integrating the coastal and marine principles developed through this work with the Scottish Government's existing terrestrial principles, reinforcing the ambition for a Source-to-Sea approach. Such integration would recognise that environmental pressures, benefits and responsibilities flow across land, coast and sea, (e.g. Scotland's 3rd Land Use Strategy). Integrated principles could help ensure that coastal and marine investment is not only effective in isolation, but also coherent within the broader context of ecosystem recovery.

From risks to opportunities: implications for policy and practice

The challenges identified above do not suggest that responsible nature finance in coastal and marine environments is unworkable. Rather, they highlight where targeted policy development, governance clarity and institutional support are most needed. For Scotland, many of these risks also represent areas of strategic opportunity: improving regulatory alignment, developing coastal and marine restoration and recovery standards, building capacity for measurement and monitoring, and strengthening benefit-sharing models. These insights have directly informed the principles proposed in this policy brief and set the stage for practical routes to embedding them in practice.

While the principles set out in this brief are not intended to prescribe scope, jurisdiction or legal application, workshop discussions underscored the importance of clarity from policymakers and regulators about how, where and by whom they are applied. Decisions about whether and how the principles extend across different types of activities, actors or marine domains sit appropriately with public authorities responsible for marine governance and regulation. Scotland already has marine governance frameworks in place, including the National Marine Plan, regional

marine planning, marine licensing (Marine Directorate with NatureScot as statutory nature conservation advisor), and seabed leasing by Crown Estate Scotland. These systems determine how marine space is used, by whom, and for what purposes, and therefore offer potential entry points for embedding the principles developed in this policy brief more broadly, not only for nature finance, but also for public authorities, developers, sectoral users and community-led initiatives whose decisions affect coastal and marine ecosystems.

Marine planning specifically provides an opportunity to embed natural capital priorities, including ecological integrity and wider ecosystem service benefits, into the allocation and management of marine space. Incorporating the principles proposed in this policy brief into the statutory marine planning process offers opportunities to align public, private, and community interests, coordinate sectoral uses, and identify priorities (spatially or thematically) for ecosystem restoration and recovery. It could also enable cross-sector collaboration and policies to avoid or minimise spatial conflict between users.

Participants noted that the principles proposed in this policy brief could be incorporated into future licensing decisions or new leasing rounds. These mechanisms already determine who can use marine space, how and for what purpose, offering a direct route for applying standards to decision-making. Embedding the principles within licensing or leasing conditions could help mainstream expectations for transparency, environmental responsibility, monitoring and engagement, especially where public resources (e.g., the seabed) are leased for private benefit. Any such development would require careful policy work and consultation with Marine Directorate, NatureScot, Crown Estate Scotland and local authorities.

Standards, codes and stewardship mechanisms

The current absence of coastal- and marine-specific metrics, governance structures and oversight mechanisms presents an opportunity to design approaches that reflect the ecological, economic and social realities of Scotland's marine and coastal environment. Workshop participants emphasised a pressing need for a dedicated, coastal and marine-specific counterpart to the terrestrial Ecosystem Restoration Code (ERC), currently under review as a follow-on to the Scottish Government's Natural Capital Market Framework and associated terrestrial principles. A Coastal and Marine Restoration and Recovery Code would need to reflect the unique dynamics of coastal and marine ecosystems, including the importance of passive recovery and pressure reduction as pathways to ecological uplift.

Participants also identified scope for a broader suite of metrics and standards spanning blue carbon, biodiversity uplift, fisheries enhancement, and water quality improvement, which could accommodate multiple forms of nature-based interventions. Importantly, this suite should not treat coastal or intertidal areas as governance grey zones: restoration, coastal retreat, and managed realignment require standards that sit comfortably across the land-sea interface.

Across discussions, participants stressed the importance of a phased and pragmatic approach to developing coastal and marine standards. There is a need to continue funding ongoing place-based pilot projects through existing mechanisms, including SMEEF (The Scottish Marine Environmental Enhancement Fund), to translate the principles proposed in this brief into practice. Large-scale pilot projects, co-designed from the outset with regulators, communities and private-sector partners, were seen as particularly valuable. These test cases allow for

experimentation with restoration actions and the supporting standards, benefit-sharing models, investment structures, monitoring approaches and engagement processes, generating learning that can inform the evolution of future standards and codes. While participants emphasised the importance of transparency, accountability and ecological integrity, there was also caution against allowing the pursuit of perfect standards, metrics or monitoring systems that delay action. In this context, early-stage investors and buyers may need to accept a degree of managed risk, recognising the wider value of contributing to market learning, ecological recovery and leadership in responsible practice. Certification and formal code alignment were viewed as essential in the longer term, but not necessarily a prerequisite for carefully governed early-stage activity.

Workshop participants consistently emphasised the potential of stewardship-based approaches in coastal and marine environments, particularly where passive recovery or pressure reduction represents the most ecologically appropriate pathway to improvement. Unlike discrete, short-term interventions, stewardship approaches focus on long-term ecosystem care, recognising that maintaining or protecting ecological condition can deliver substantial ecological benefit even where measurable uplift is gradual, uncertain or spatially diffuse.

A range of financial and non-financial mechanisms could be developed to support stewardship approaches. These may include stewardship payments^{21, 22}, ecosystem service contracts (analogous to environmentally friendly agri-environment schemes on land), or, where appropriate, credit-based mechanisms. One emerging concept discussed was stewardship credits, defined as representing a measurable unit of ecological conservation or improvement combined with social progress, capturing a broader spectrum of ecosystem and community benefits than single-outcome credits (Social Carbon, 2025). A second example is the Reef Credit Scheme in Australia, one of the first mechanisms that captures the Source-to-Sea framing²³. It is designed to improve water quality entering the Great Barrier Reef. The scheme enables farmers and landholders to receive payments for actions that reduce nutrient or sediment run-off, with outcomes independently verified and translated into “Reef Credits.” Investors, including corporates and philanthropic organisations, purchase these credits as a means of supporting measurable environmental improvements while meeting sustainability or responsibility objectives.

Participants also cautioned that stewardship approaches raise important questions around additionality, especially where interventions are designed to prevent degradation rather than generate new, quantifiable outcomes. In coastal and marine contexts, additionality may therefore need to be interpreted more flexibly, recognising actions that demonstrably reduce credible threats, sustain ecosystem condition, or enable recovery trajectories that would otherwise be unlikely to occur, rather than relying solely on short-term changes against static baselines. International experience was seen as offering useful, if cautionary, lessons. Models such as REDD+ (Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation in developing countries) in forest conservation highlight the importance of transparent baselining, attention to leakage and permanence, and long-term institutional commitment. At the same time, participants were clear that weaknesses in some REDD+ implementations have undermined trust in carbon markets. This reinforces the need for stewardship approaches in coastal and marine settings to be developed with a clear understanding of these risks.

Any stewardship-based mechanisms would require careful research, piloting and adaptation in Scottish coastal and marine contexts. They could enable compensation for actors such as fishers, coastal community organisations, farmers or local authorities for maintaining or improving ecosystem functions, even where benefits are not directly monetisable or readily tradeable. By shifting the financial logic from “pay for performance” to “pay for protection and long-term care,” stewardship approaches reflect the shared, sustained and preventative nature of coastal and marine ecosystem management.

Oversight, registries and institutional capacity

Experience from compliance and voluntary led interventions on land highlights the need for coordinating body with responsibility for mapping interventions, monitoring outcomes and reporting on risks, and preferably this oversight should be independent, publicly accessible and regularly updated^{24,25}.

In Scotland, there is a need to clarify the potential roles of existing institutions. For example, SEPA has a statutory mandate for environmental monitoring and integrity, while Crown Estate Scotland and the Marine Directorate hold core responsibilities in leasing and licensing marine activity. However, these bodies already operate under significant resource constraints, and expanding mandates would require additional funding, data capacity and staffing. Any governance model should therefore be designed to minimise administrative burden and avoid placing disproportionate responsibility on organisations that also have regulatory, licensing or revenue-raising roles. Independence and separation of functions is important for avoiding conflicts of interest and ensuring that oversight is legitimate, transparent and trusted.

Resourcing should be understood in the broadest possible sense, not only as investment in individual restoration sites, but also in the systems that support effective governance: long-term ecological monitoring, science capacity, data infrastructure, community engagement, marine planning, fisheries management and evaluation. These are essential foundations for ensuring that coastal and marine stewardship delivers ecological integrity, social value and public accountability. One idea raised at the workshop was “Research-linked credits” where revenue generated from investment could play a role in resourcing this work, particularly when routed through academic partnerships or agencies responsible for long-term data stewardship.

A transparent, public-facing registry of coastal and marine interventions, stewardship activities, outcomes and finance flows would help to strengthen legitimacy and provide a traceable record of activity across land, coast and sea. Such a registry could complement existing terrestrial registries (e.g. UK Carbon Registry). SMEEF is one potential vehicle for this. In the previous example of Reef Credits in Australia, the scheme is administered by Eco-Markets, an independent, not-for-profit body that manages the standard, registers projects, and ensures that environmental outcomes are monitored, measured and verified. The purpose of such a registry is not only to support nature finance, but to provide a unified, evidence-based record of where activity is occurring, what outcomes are being realised, and how benefits and responsibilities are shared.

Participants also highlighted the importance of ensuring that future pathways to investment are straightforward and well-signposted. If multiple funding mechanisms, licences or approval processes operate in parallel, this may increase transaction costs, create uncertainty, or deter

private participation. Clarity, coordination and streamlined routes will therefore be important considerations as Scotland moves from pilots to operational delivery. In this context, the emerging Nature Investment Prospectus (planned for launch in 2026) may provide a valuable signposting function, helping investors identify high-integrity opportunities and understand how different routes to investment connect.

Social value, benefit-sharing and adaptive stewardship

Finally, workshop participants consistently emphasised that translating principles from land to coast and sea is not only a technical exercise in ecological framing and governance, but also a deeply social one. Models of benefit-sharing developed for terrestrial settings often rely on geographically fixed communities and are therefore poorly suited to coastal and marine environments, where benefits and impacts are frequently diffuse, widely shared and difficult to quantify. These include public goods such as climate regulation, coastal protection, cultural value, biodiversity resilience and ecosystem functioning. In nearshore contexts, benefits may also include more place-based outcomes such as local employment, skills development, education, infrastructure and long-term stewardship arrangements, aligning closely with Scotland's current discussions on Community Wealth Building.

Ensuring that these social and environmental benefits are recognised, valued and equitably distributed is central to the legitimacy of nature finance and wider marine decision-making. In this brief, social effectiveness is understood to encompass both place-based community benefits and wider societal benefits, recognising that coastal and marine ecosystems deliver public value across scales and that affected communities may be dispersed, overlapping or not geographically fixed.

Participants also highlighted that engagement in marine contexts must extend beyond one-off consultation or benefit-sharing discussions. Meaningful social outcomes depend on sustained, transparent and appropriately resourced engagement processes that may, depending on context, include involvement in agenda-setting, project design, management arrangements or adaptive decision-making over time. While the specific scope of engagement will vary by project and governance setting, the need for mechanisms that support ongoing dialogue, responsiveness and trust was seen as critical to maintaining legitimacy and social licence.

Underpinning all of this is the need for a pragmatic and adaptive approach. While ambition is essential, so too is realism about current capacities, regulatory gaps and ecological uncertainty. Not every approach will be perfect, and learning by doing will be unavoidable. This is precisely why the Principles for Responsible Investment in Coastal and Marine Natural Capital matter. Although the workshop initially focused on adapting terrestrial principles to support coastal and marine restoration, discussions made clear that these principles have broader relevance across the full spectrum of marine uses — from conservation and restoration to offshore renewables, aquaculture and coastal infrastructure. The principles therefore provide a shared framework to guide emerging practice, align investment with ecological integrity and social wellbeing, and ensure that public value remains central to marine space allocation and long-term stewardship.

Annex 2 Theory of Change: embedding principles for responsible investment across land, coast, and sea

This annex outlines the Theory of Change underpinning the development and use of the Principles for Responsible Investment in Coastal and Marine Natural Capital.

Context and rationale: Robust principles are essential to guide marine and coastal natural capital investment, ensuring it evolves in ways that are ecologically credible, socially just, and aligned with source-to-sea principles for efficiencies and synergies with the parallel terrestrial framework.

Intervention: This policy brief introduces revised and new principles for responsible marine and coastal investment, co-developed through cross-sector consultation. The principles provide a values-based framework to shape future investment in line with ecological complexity, system connectivity, and community benefit.

Assumptions: This theory of change is based on the following assumptions:

- Scottish Government, NatureScot and other regulatory and statutory bodies, and market actors are open to adopting and embedding revised principles into planning, licensing, and funding processes
- The principles can support the co-development of credible codes, standards, and registries for marine and coastal protection, restoration and recovery
- Natural capital principles can guide not only investors, but also planners, communities, and policymakers in delivering high-integrity outcomes
- The Source-to-Sea framing creates an opportunity to revisit terrestrial principles and embed wider environmental, social, and cultural objectives

Enablers:

Internal enablers (within control of government or partners):

- Scottish Government's PINC Programme and cross-agency coordination (e.g. Marine Directorate, NatureScot, Crown Estate Scotland)
- Alignment with emerging code development (e.g. Ecosystem Restoration Code)
- Greater coherence, efficiencies and synergies, between land and marine planning frameworks

External enablers (beyond direct control):

- Investor demand for high-integrity and transparent frameworks
- Growing public interest in coastal and marine restoration, enhancement and protection
- International learning from high-integrity marine finance pilots

Activities:

- Publish and disseminate revised principles through this brief and wider policy engagement

- Support the development of marine restoration codes and registries aligned with the principles
- Raise awareness and build understanding across sectors

Outputs:

- A published set of Principles for Responsible Investment in Coastal and Marine Natural Capital.

Outcomes

Near-term outcomes

- A shared understanding of what constitutes high-integrity coastal and marine natural capital investment
- Increased clarity for policymakers, regulators, practitioners and investors on best practice
- Identification of key gaps in policy, governance and infrastructure (e.g. codes, registries, oversight)

Medium-term outcomes

- Stronger and more coherent governance arrangements aligned with the principles
- Development of verification approaches, codes and investment frameworks that reflect marine and coastal realities
- More transparent, credible and legitimate approaches to mobilising finance for restoration and resilience

Longer-term impacts

- High-integrity, inclusive and transparent coastal and marine natural capital markets
- Sustained restoration and protection of marine ecosystems and biodiversity
- Fairer distribution of benefits and strengthened resilience for coastal communities and wider society
- A more coherent, system-wide Source-to-Sea approach embedded across Scotland's natural capital governance

Annex 3: Glossary

Additionality: The requirement that an environmental benefit (e.g. carbon sequestration or biodiversity gain) would not have occurred without the investment or intervention. Essential for ensuring credits represent real and meaningful outcomes.

Baseline: A reference state of ecological, social, or economic conditions used to measure change or impact from a project. In marine settings, baselines are often uncertain or lacking due to limited data.

Blue Bonds: A type of debt instrument used to raise capital for marine conservation or sustainable ocean-based activities. Often supported by public or philanthropic guarantees.

Bundling and Stacking: Methods of combining multiple ecosystem service benefits into a single (bundled) or multiple (stacked) credit products—e.g. carbon, biodiversity, and water quality credits from one project.

Community Benefit: The economic, social, or cultural advantages that accrue to a local or affected community as a result of natural capital investment. In marine contexts, community may be geographically dispersed or non-residential.

Compliance Market: A legally mandated market where participants are required to meet environmental targets (e.g. carbon emissions). Often more effective than voluntary markets due to enforceable standards and penalties.

Ecosystem Services: The benefits that people derive from ecosystems, including provisioning (e.g. seafood), regulating (e.g. climate regulation), cultural (e.g. heritage), and supporting (e.g. nutrient cycling) services.

Environmental Integrity: The principle that investments and credits must result in real, verifiable, and lasting ecological benefits without causing harm elsewhere.

Fungibility: The ability of a credit or asset to be interchangeable with others of the same kind, which supports liquidity and ease of trading in nature markets.

Just Transition: A framework for ensuring that environmental and economic shifts do not disadvantage vulnerable or marginalised groups, and instead support fair outcomes and inclusive participation.

Marine Planning: A policy process to coherently manage the diverse use of marine space, activities and resources, balancing ecological protection and enhancement with economic and social objectives.

Mitigation Hierarchy: A framework for reducing environmental harm through a sequence of actions: avoid, minimise, restore, and offset. Used to guide responsible investment in biodiversity and habitat.

Natural Capital: The stock of natural resources and ecosystems (e.g. forests, wetlands, oceans) that provide ecosystem services. Viewed as an asset class in emerging environmental finance frameworks.

Nature Markets: Markets that facilitate the buying and selling of ecosystem services or nature-based outcomes, such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity gain, or water quality improvements.

Passive Restoration: An approach that relies on reducing human pressures to allow natural recovery of ecosystems, rather than direct interventions like planting or engineering.

Pressure Reduction: The removal or limitation of damaging human activities (e.g. bottom trawling, pollution) to enable ecosystem recovery.

Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital: A set of Scottish Government-endorsed guidelines outlining how private investment in natural capital should be conducted to ensure public value, transparency, and ecological integrity.

Stewardship Credits: Emerging credit types that reward the ongoing protection and maintenance of ecosystems, rather than just outcomes from active restoration.

Voluntary Market: A market in which entities choose (rather than are required) to invest in environmental outcomes, such as carbon offsetting or biodiversity credits. Standards vary widely.

About MASTS: Formed in 2009, the Marine Alliance for Science and Technology for Scotland is a consortium of 18 organisations engaged in marine science and represents the majority of Scotland's marine research capacity. MASTS Research Forums and Working Groups form the major scientific driving force of the MASTS community, serving as platforms of expertise, networking and knowledge exchange.

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